

Effects of continuous improvement in streamlining HRM practices

Wickramasinghe, V.

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Chathurani, M.N.

Department of Management of Technology, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka.

Citation:

Wickramasinghe, V., & Chathurani, M.N. (2021), Effects of continuous improvement in streamlining HRM practices, Business Process Management Journal, 27(3), 883-900. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/BPMJ-03-2020-0130>

This Version is available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/BPMJ-03-2020-0130>

Effects of continuous improvement in streamlining HRM practices

Abstract

Purpose- The present study investigated the effect of continuous improvement initiatives in streamlining HRM practices in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach- Survey methodology was used and 217 respondents who fulfilled the selection criteria set for the study responded. Structural equation modelling was performed to examine the hypothesized relationships.

Findings- The analysis supported the hypotheses that continuous improvement initiatives significantly positively influence to streamline HRM practices of performance management, job-related training, employee involvement and team work.

Practical implications- Continuous improvement initiatives that are aligned with the strategic direction of firms guide to design and implement better focused HRM practices.

Originality/value- The failure to streamline HRM practices in accordance with continuous improvement initiatives has been identified as a key barrier for the effective utilization of human resources. Although continuous improvement initiatives demand changes in the way HRM is practiced, so far, little empirical attention has been paid to understand the implications of continuous improvement initiatives for HRM practices.

Keywords: Continuous improvement, employee involvement, human resource management practices, job-related training, performance management, team work.

Introduction

Continuous improvement (CI) associates with the implementation of incremental and continual changes to existing practices aimed at improving the performance of product or service delivery to experience long-lasting changes in organizations leading to its survival and growth (Gonzalez and Martins, 2016; Marin-Garcia et al., 2008; Tanco et al., 2012). Berling (2000, p. S484) defined CI as “one of the activities whereby processes and procedures are implemented, which contribute to organizational goals through the continuous improvement of work processes,

workplaces and work interactions”. Today, the implementation of CI initiatives is evident across all types and sizes of organizations worldwide (Bhuiyan and Baghel, 2005; Gonzalez and Martins, 2016; Matthews and Marzec, 2017). Continuous improvement methodologies, in general, involved with incremental improvements of low risk and low capital investments such as conformance and standardization (Berling, 2000; Brown et al., 2008; Jurburg et al., 2018). However, over the years, methodologies such as lean and balanced score card have also become prominent (Bhuiyan and Baghel, 2005; Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2016).

Irrespective of the types of CI methodologies adopted, the launch of CI initiatives implies a transformation from centralization to decentralization, which demands the involvement of all employees in making incremental improvements (Glover et al., 2011; Jurburg et al., 2018). In this regard, some previous studies argue that improvements in HRM practices are the driving force in making incremental changes in organizational processes (e.g., Jimenez-Jimenez and Martinez-Costa, 2009; Rijnders and Boer, 2004). However, this position could be challenged based on the recent arguments in the literature on both CI and HRM (such as Cooke and Kim, 2018; Hur, 2009; Liao et al., 2011; Mariappanadar and Kramar, 2014; Ramayah et al., 2011; Sparrow and Otake-Ebede, 2014; Wickramasinghe, 2012; Wickramasinghe and Mahmood, 2018; Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2016). For example, Cooke and Kim (2018) suggest that less developed countries in Asia are left with few options to survive and thrive in a complex and unpredictable global environment, and their preferred HRM practices are conditioned by the global competitive environment. Wickramasinghe and Mahmood (2018) provide specific evidence that firms in Sri Lanka and Bangladesh are in a process of replacing traditional long-term employment with a new, short-term, transactional deal to employ personnel in the most efficient manner. According to Wickramasinghe and Mahmood (2018), although HRM practices are considered as a source of competitive advantage, private sector organizations in both countries are yet to fully appreciate these developments. Further, it is evident in the less developed countries that human resource manager’s role has not yet evolved to the level of strategic and they are playing a symbolic role on the board (Wickramasinghe and Mahmood, 2018; Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2016). This situation mainly prevails due to deficiencies in competency, education and the experience of HR managers for them to practice strategic HRM (Dharmasiri, 2004; Sajeewanie and Opatha, 2007). In this regard, Wickramasinghe and Mahmood (2018), Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe (2016) and Sparrow and Otake-Ebede (2014) provide evidence for very high involvement of line managers in the delivery of HRM practices in the implementation of CI initiatives than that of HR managers. Further, the involvement of finance department, system analysts and the IT division

of organizations were identified to acquire a prominent role in reporting HR information (Wickramasinghe and Mahmood, 2018). In this context, it is more valid to argue that the HRM functions of developing countries lack capacity to innovate, initiate and drive CI initiatives, and the need of business survival in local and export markets is the driving force in the implementation of CI initiatives. In this regard, scholars such as Sparrow and Otaye-Ebede (2014), Wickramasinghe (2012), Ramayah et al. (2011), Hur (2009) and Abdullah et al. (2009) argue that it is the requirements of CI that affect the adoption of innovative HRM practices. When building on this line of reasoning, business organizations in the developing world, many with cost differentiation strategies of market orientation, may not introduce innovative HRM practices unless there is a compelling need of business survival and growth. Mariappanadar and Kramar (2014) suggest that this root of improvement in HRM practices may also lead to develop some sustainable people management practices in organizations.

Present study, research question and purpose. In line with the background of the present study discussed in the above section, it is important to investigate whether CI initiatives operate as a driving force in streamlining HRM practices. In this regard, studies such as Glover et al. (2011), Hur (2009) and Vouzas (2007) imply that failure to streamline HRM practices in accordance with CI initiatives operate as a key barrier for the effective utilization of human resources in the context of CI. The streamlining of existing HRM practices as a result of CI may improve employees' performance, get their involvement in the modification of organizational processes, create collective responsibility for performance and strengthen the coordination of cross-functional skills. Therefore, we question, "Do CI initiatives have a positive effect in making changes in the HRM practices of performance management, job-related training, employee involvement and teamwork?" Accordingly, the purpose of our study is to investigate the effect of CI initiatives in streamlining these HRM practices.

Importance of the study. We identify the research question raised above and the purpose of our study as timely and important since to date little empirical attention has been paid to understand the implications of CI initiatives for HRM practices (e.g., Wickramasinghe, 2012). As a result, there is little evidence for the organizations' understanding of streamlining HRM practices to accommodate the requirements of CI. Further, so far, little empirical attention has been paid to understand implications of CI initiatives for HRM practices in developing countries (see Wickramasinghe, 2012; Wickramasinghe and Mahmood, 2018). Hence, the role of CI in

streamlining HRM practices in the context of a developing country could provide valuable information for academics, practitioners and policy makers worldwide.

Furthermore, the present study investigated the effect of CI on HRM practices in the context of service delivery. The provision of excellent service is a profitable strategy that results in increased customer satisfaction and loyalty, the attraction of new customers, market growth and sustained corporate performance (Hur, 2009; Lombardi et al., 2020). Yet, any improvements in the service provision demands constant enhancement of internal efficiencies (Milner and Savage, 2016). This implies that improvements in the level of service provision demand changes in the utilization of human resources even though changes to HRM practices are not the original target of the initiative (Glover et al., 2011; Hur, 2009; Abdullah et al., 2009). Therefore, the implementation of CI initiatives in service organizations requires changes in the way human resource is managed. However, the majority of previous studies investigated the effects of CI in the context of manufacturing (e.g., Jurburg et al., 2018; Turesky and Connell, 2010; Wickramasinghe, 2012); it is very rare to find studies in the context of services. Service provision is concerned with how a particular service is delivered and thereby experience connected with the service delivery (Grönroos, 2001). The service delivery ultimately influences how employees are utilized - the way they make decisions, their job-related training and steps taken to streamline their job performance. However, we have not come across previous research that investigated the effects of CI on HRM practices in the context of service delivery.

Overall, changes occurring in HRM practices due to CI initiatives appear to be far from conclusive and present challenges for CI and HRM advocates in effective decision-making. Therefore, more research studies are needed in this important area.

Research design in brief. Building on the existing literature, hypotheses were developed to empirically test the relationship between CI initiatives and HRM practices. As presented and discussed at length in the section on “Methodology”, quantitative research method was chosen for the study and a survey was administered to collect the data. Structural equation modelling was performed for the data analysis.

Paper plan. The next section reviews the theoretical background of the study. The methodology used in the study is then presented. Thereafter, results are presented and discussed along with implications to theory and practice. Finally, conclusions are presented followed by the limitations of the study and areas for future research.

Review of literature

Continuous improvement

Continuous improvement of work processes, work places and work interactions describe a management philosophy in which all employees actively continually seeking out and eliminating the sources of process imperfection using a bottom-up approach (Ni and Sun, 2009; Wynder, 2008). Bessant and Caffyn (1997, p. 2) defined CI as “an organization-wide process of focused and sustained incremental innovation”. Boer et al. (2000, p. xvi) provided the most comprehensive and widely accepted definition, in which CI is “the planned, organized and systematic process of on-going, incremental and company-wide change of existing practices aimed at improving company performance”. According to Boer et al. (2000), the key features of CI are widespread employee involvement and low risk, cost and investment in the adoption. These features coincide with previous research that conceptualized CI as a tool for competitive advantage (such as Berling, 2000; Prado-Prado, 2009).

Brown et al. (2008) identified two strands of CI methodologies as continuous productivity improvement and continuous quality improvement. Examples for continuous productivity improvement methodologies include lean production and balanced score card while examples for continuous quality improvement methodologies include quality standards and TQM (Glover et al., 2011). Previous research showed that larger/well-established organizations tend to focus on methodologies such as TQM while smaller/newer organizations tend to focus on regulatory compliance (Brown et al., 2008). Bhuiyan and Baghel (2005) and Brown et al. (2008) identified a trend towards implementing a combination of CI methodologies such as lean six-sigma instead of confined to a particular methodology. Such hybrid methodologies are favoured to overcome the weaknesses of one methodology over the other (Bhuiyan and Baghel, 2005). Further, some organizations have developed their own CI methodologies based on their specific business needs such as Toyota Production System (see Berling, 2000).

As a result of numerous incremental improvements, an organization could yield important and lasting improvements over time, such as improvements in productivity (Rapp and Eklund, 2002), quality (Brown et al., 2008), the reduction of production costs (Terziovski and Sohal, 2000) or the time of manufacture (Prado-Prado, 2009). In this regard, Graso and Probst (2012) and Ni and Sun (2009) suggest that the ultimate outcome of incremental and continual improvements are to shift the organization from operational objectives (like productivity and quality) to strategic competitive advantage (like sustainable dynamic capability). Hence, CI can be considered as a process improvement mechanism with strategic importance.

For the success of CI, the involvement of all employees in making incremental improvements is vital. Hence, the launch of CI implies a transformation from centralization to decentralization, which demands changes to how human resource (HR) is managed at work (Mariappanadar and Kramar, 2014; Ni and Sun, 2009). The present study investigated CI in the context of service delivery, unlike production settings such as lean manufacturing. The aim of any service system is delivering a high-quality service that satisfies customers. Psychological and behavioural aspects such as ways in which service employees perform their tasks, treating customers as individuals, understanding what customers need beforehand, showing willingness to help and the speed of delivery are some of the important aspects of service delivery (Grönroos, 2001; McCain et al., 2005). Accordingly, the process aspects of how services are provided have been identified as a strength that could outperform competitors (Samat et al., 2006). Therefore, any improvements of service delivery demand constant improvements of internal efficiencies including the way HR is managed.

Continuous improvement and HRM practices

An organization's CI strategy is an important determinant of its HRM strategy that directs the way in which employees are utilized. For example, the way they are trained, steps taken to streamline job performance and their involvement in decision-making (Mariappanadar and Kramar, 2014; Monks et al., 1997; Petrick and Furr, 1995; Wickramasinghe, 2012). In this regard, the literature suggests that the implementation of CI initiatives demands changes in the practices of performance management (Graso and Probst, 2012), training (Ni and Sun, 2009), employee involvement (Wynder, 2008) and team work (Berling, 2000). Wickramasinghe (2012, p. 836) provided evidence for making changes within the HR department by upgrading the role of HRM function and by redesigning several HRM practices concurrently, such as performance management and competence development, to bring these in line with TQM. Sometimes, the effective implementation of CI initiatives demands substantial changes in the practices of performance management, job-related training, employee involvement and teamwork even though changes to HRM practices are not the original target of the initiative (Hur, 2009; Monks et al., 1997; Wickramasinghe, 2012). Hence, when organizations aim towards CI they have to adopt more productive and constructive approach for the management of human resources by re-designing and streamlining existing HRM practices to fit into CI initiatives (Vouzas, 2004; Wickramasinghe, 2012). Overall, these studies imply the importance of HRM function in adopting more constructive approach to the way of managing human resources by introducing process improvements in accordance with CI objectives. Building on the literature on CI and

HRM, which were reviewed earlier, performance management, job-related training, employee involvement and teamwork practices were identified to investigate the ways in which CI initiatives influence these practices. Accordingly, following sections review the specific literature on these practices to support our arguments.

Performance management. Performance management involves a set of integrated activities performed by a firm such as setting expectations, reviewing results and rewarding performance to enhance the performance of employees (DeNisi, 2011; Gravina and Siers, 2011). A firm's performance management should be based on performance targets or key performance indicators by translating organizational strategies into operational terms (Gravina and Siers, 2011). Further, it should be able to provide valid and useful information to make the decisions of rewards administration, employee retention/termination and potential (Biron et al., 2011; Shrivastava and Purang, 2011).

The literature on CI and HRM such as Çiçek et al. (2005), Graso and Probst (2012), Hur (2009), Petrick and Furr (1995), Soltani et al. (2006) and Wickramasinghe (2012) imply the importance of adjusting performance management practices to integrate with chosen CI initiatives. For example, Soltani et al. (2006, p. 92) state "by acquiring the relevant knowledge and understanding of contextually appropriate performance appraisal and management, practitioners would be able to translate TQM requirements into performance appraisal criteria to maintain the integrity of organizational change initiatives aimed at long-term business excellence". Further, Petrick and Furr (1995) stated that performance management should be in line with continuous quality improvement initiatives, and suggested the need of total quality appraisal based on quality driven performance appraisal. This implies the need of bringing performance appraisal in accordance with CI initiatives. Furthermore, the study by Çiçek et al. (2005) emphasized the importance of adjusting performance measurement to incorporate team performance since CI initiatives demand a higher level of team involvement. However, such theoretical arguments are rarely supported by adequate empirical research that investigated the influence of CI on performance management. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H1: The implementation of CI initiatives has a positive effect on the practices of performance management.

Job-related training. Job-related training put a premium on the development of new skills and learning abilities to enhance organizational flexibility by building broader repertoires of skills and behaviours possessed by employees. Hence, job-related training is a conscious endeavour

within an organization to translate learning processes to meet present and future organizational requirements. Job-related training can address different elements of the job to prepare employees to meet present and future organizational requirements while extending the scope of organizational capabilities (Liao et al., 2011). Training helps to develop a workforce capable of shouldering increased responsibility, build trust among employees, develop multi-skilled workers, increase employee participation and cooperation, and foster knowledge sharing (Turesky and Connell, 2010).

The literature on CI and HRM such as Berling (2000), Hassan et al. (2006), Hur (2009), Kaye and Anderson (1999), Ni and Sun (2009), Wickramasinghe (2012), Jaca et al. 2016), Gonzalez and Martins (2016) and Matthews and Marzec (2017) provide strong support for the need of strengthening training provided to employees in accordance with CI requirements. For instance, Kaye and Anderson (1999) stated that firms adopted Investors in People standard to integrate training with CI initiatives. Further, Monks et al. (1997) stated that training activities should be more focused towards CI initiatives, and they showed that the changes made to employee training were the most widespread across their study sample compared to the changes made to other HRM practices (such as recruitment and selection) during the implementation of CI initiatives. Hassan et al. (2006) showed the importance of coaching and knowledge sharing mechanisms to support CI initiatives. Jaca et al. (2016) showed the importance of a readiness programme aimed at improving employees' awareness for the sustainability of CI initiatives. Matthews and Marzec (2017) and Gonzalez and Martins (2016) showed that CI initiatives demand employees to learn continuously for the sustainability of CI initiatives. However, as reviewed above, only few empirical studies supported the influence of CI on job-related training. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H2: The implementation of CI initiatives has a positive effect on the practices of job-related training.

Employee involvement. Employee involvement is an individual's level of psychological identification with the specific job to which he or she is engaged or absorbed in (Kanungo, 1985). Employee involvement is designed to empower employees to make decisions and solve problems appropriate to their job level in the organization (Wynder, 2008). Hence, it manifests in many forms, such as active involvement in root cause problem solving to maximize added value, the adaptation of work teams to variations in job duties, the exchange of positions within the work group and the habit of giving each other a hand in the moments of difficulty (see de Treville and Antonakis, 2006).

The literature on CI such as Wynder (2008), Jurburg et al. (2018) and Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe (2011) provided support for the influence of CI on employee involvement practices. For example, Jurburg et al. (2018) showed that CI initiatives influence employee involvement in a study of manufacturing organizations. The implementation of CI initiatives requires employees to re-conceptualize the boundaries of their jobs and engage in new behaviours (Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe, 2011; Wynder, 2008). The underlying assumption of employee involvement in the context of CI is that employees closest to a problem are in the best position to make decisions for improvement; they should be involved in decision-making processes. Hence, Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe (2011) argue that organizations implementing CI initiatives should make changes to decision-making processes to encourage employee involvement and to adopt shared responsibility. The studies of Vouzas (2004) and Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe (2011) showed that if organizations fail to provide employees with autonomy for decision-making at their job levels, their involvement will be limited to suggestions for improvement. However, these arguments in the literature need to be supported adequately by empirical evidence. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H3: The implementation of CI initiatives has a positive effect on the practices of employee involvement.

Team work. Team-based work arrangements are identified as one of the best means to achieve flexibility and versatility (Haas, 2010). The many facets of team processes can be identified in a team working environment such as the degree of experienced friendliness, support, ability to cope and positive contribution to sustain a healthy team working environment (Bourgault et al., 2008). Team work creates a culture that promotes co-operation, collaboration, mutual support and social interaction between team members (Dayan and Di Benedetto, 2009; Ketkar and Sett, 2009; Tjosvold, 1984).

The literature supports the need of streamlining team work practices in accordance with CI initiatives (Berling, 2000; Hur, 2009; Marin-Garcia et al., 2008). For example, Marin-Garcia et al. (2008) argued that teams could be designed to meet the needs of on-going CI responsibilities as well as to meet the needs of CI initiatives spanning for a predetermined duration. Wickramasinghe and Wickramasinghe (2011) argue that in a CI environment teams should be designed for team members to adopt team-based decision making and information sharing as an inherent part of their job. However, the effect of CI on team work has not been supported adequately with empirical evidence. Therefore, it is hypothesized:

H4: The implementation of CI initiatives has a positive effect on the practices of team work.

Methodology

In line with the purpose of the study, the literature has been reviewed and four hypotheses have been proposed to test the relationship between CI and each HRM practice. Quantitative research method was chosen as the most appropriate methodological approach to test the hypotheses. It is expected that the quantitative method would support the generalisation and replication of findings. The collection of empirical data is identified as an important part of the present study. The survey was identified as the main method of data collection since present study is cross-sectional in nature in contrast to longitudinal. Below sections present and describe in detail the selection of sample, the method of data collection, measures used and the methods of data analysis.

Sample

Our population of interest was mobile and fixed line telecommunication firms that had implemented CI initiatives in the service provision in Sri Lanka. We selected this industry since it is the fastest growing service sector in the country and a pioneer in the South Asian region for being the first to introduce several latest technologies. By the time of the study, there were seven (7) telecommunication firms in operation, and all the firms agreed to participate in the survey. All the firms had implemented CI initiatives and running these for at least two years continuously by the time of the survey. With regard to the characteristics of the responding firms, the oldest firm was established in the year 1990 while the youngest firm was established in the year 2008. All the telecommunication firms had dedicated HR department and CI policy in operation. Eighty-eight per cent of the respondents were from telecommunication firms that had separate division responsible for implementing CI initiatives. All the firms had implemented formal CI initiatives (refer to Table 1 and Table 2) and running these for at least two years continuously by the time of the survey. Our unit of analysis is managerial-level employees exposed to CI initiatives and changes occurred thereafter. In this regard, Spector (1994) suggests that despite the weaknesses of cross-sectional self-report methodology at individual-level, this design can be quite useful in providing a picture of and inter-correlations among people's job environment and their reactions to job contexts, which can be useful for deriving hypotheses about how people react to jobs. To ease the data collection, a contact person representing each firm was identified. The contact person from each firm together with one of the authors of this

paper randomly selected a cross-section of managerial-level employees from each firm. Further, they were aware of CI initiatives in their respective firms, involved in implementing them and exposed to any changes in HRM practices. Self-administered survey questionnaire was distributed among the above mentioned seven firms covering at least 10% from each firm, and not more than 5% were selected from the same department/unit. We distributed 345 questionnaires using stratified random sampling method. The anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension. Of the total number of questionnaires distributed, a total of 217 responses were received at the end of the data collection period, yielding a response rate of 63%. These responses reflected a representative sample of target respondents mentioned above.

With regard to the characteristics of respondents, 66% were male while 34% were female. Forty-seven per cent were from the age range of 21-30 years, 49% were from the age range of 31-40 years and 4% were above 41 years of age. Sixty-five per cent had bachelor's degree as the highest level of qualification (equating to the level 5 of Sri Lanka Qualification Framework [SLQF]) while the remaining reported diploma as the highest level of qualification (equating to the level 4 of SLQF). With regard to the years of experience in the present workplace, 9% had more than one but less than two years of experience, 65% had more than two but less than five years of experience, 22% had more than five but less than 10 years of experience and 4% had more than 10 years of experience.

Measures

The implementation of CI initiatives. We used two mechanisms to identify item measures of CI. First, we used prior theoretical and empirical work reviewed earlier. In this regard, we found that Turesky and Connell (2010) and Wickramasinghe (2012) treated CI as the independent variable in their studies. We also found the studies of Grönroos (2001), Kaye and Anderson (1999) and Bhuiyan and Baghel, (2005) useful in the conceptualization of CI. Although none of these studies provided already constructed and tested item measures to be used in our study, we found these prior studies as useful in the development of item measures for our study. Second, parallel to the review of literature, we did a preliminary investigation into CI initiatives in Sri Lanka. Thereafter, the items were first, assessed by a panel of academics and practitioners to ensure the face and content validity. Second, the items were pre-tested with a sample of appropriate employees. The 7-item measure developed by us for the present study is given in Appendix 1. The measure is on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree, where higher scores indicate a higher level of achievement.

Performance management. Our intention was to identify employees' perception regarding their exposure to performance management that had been implemented by enterprises. We followed the same procedure mentioned above to finalize the item measures. In the process, we found that the study of Soltani et al. (2006) is insightful since the literature reviewed earlier had not provided already constructed and tested item measures appropriate for the present study. The 7-item measure developed by us for the present study is given in Appendix 1. This measure is on a five-point Likert response scale ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree.

Job-related training. We captured employees' perception regarding their exposure to job-related training that had been implemented by enterprises. We followed the same procedure mentioned above to finalize the item measures. In the process, we found that the study of Kaye and Anderson (1999) is useful in the conceptualization of job-related training in the context of CI. The 6-item measure developed by us for the present study is given in Appendix 1. This measure used a five-point Likert response scale as described earlier.

Employee involvement. Our intention was to capture employees' perception regarding their exposure to employee involvement that had been practiced by enterprises. We followed the same procedure mentioned above to finalize the item measures. In the process, we found that the study of De Val and Lloyd (2003) is insightful in conceptualizing the measure. The 5-item measure developed by us for the present study is given in Appendix 1. This measure used a five-point Likert response scale as described earlier.

Team work. We captured employees' perception regarding their exposure to team work that had been used by enterprises. We followed the same procedure mentioned above to finalize the item measures. In the process, we found that the study of Hoegl and Gemuenden (2001) is useful in the conceptualization of team work. The 5-item measure developed by us for the present study is given in Appendix 1. This measure used a five-point Likert response scale as described earlier.

In addition to the above mentioned main variables of the study, we collected data on *CI methodologies in use (see Table 1)*, *the types of teams in operation (see Table 2)*, *the average number of training hours provided per employee per year*, and *the average number of different training programmes provided per employee per year* using nominal scales for descriptive statistics.

Methods of data analysis

Initial data screening and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) were conducted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The variables were mean centred to increase the

interpretability of relationships. We tested EFA for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure, (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity, and (e) construct reliability to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias; convergent validity was measured by the average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE following the recommended guidelines and thresholds of Hair et al. (2009). As shown in Appendix 1, variables demonstrated good internal consistency reliability, factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity and construct reliability. Wilks' Lambda statistic was obtained to check whether any differences exist across the firms. The results revealed that significant differences do not exist ($p > 0.05$) across the firms on our study variables (refer to Hair et al., 2009). This non-existence of differences is the foundation for us to proceed with hypotheses testing. To examine the hypothesized relationships, structural equation modelling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation was performed using AMOS. Fit measures relating to absolute fit (CMIN/df, GFI), relative fit (CFI), parsimonious fit (PRATIO) and fit measures based on the non-central chi-square distribution (RMSEA, PCLOSE) were used to evaluate the model-data fit, following the recommended procedures of Arbuckle (2007).

Findings of the study

The descriptive statistics for CI methodologies in use are shown in Table 1. Firms had implemented more than one CI methodology; the most popular CI methodology is ISO 9000: 2008.

Table 1

With regard to the descriptive statistics for the provision of formal job-related training, the average number of training hours provided per employee per year was 26 hours (SD = 3.16). The average number of different training programs provided per employee per year was 8 (SD = 2.44). Table 2 shows descriptive statistics for the types of teams in operation. Table 2 suggests that the majority of respondents were attached to process improvement teams. These were formally established teams where participation in improvement activities becomes the expected rather than the exception with the active support of the management. The second rated team type was quality circles, which were formally established to solve problems and make improvements related to specific job contexts. The scope of this team was much narrower than process

improvement teams. The third ranked team type was workplace improvement teams, where a team of volunteer employees took the ownership of simple and low risk improvements in the workplace. The least popular team type was corrective action teams, where management inaugurated these teams to find solutions for a pre-defined problem.

Table 2

The means, standard deviations and correlations for the study variables are shown in Table 3.

Table 3

The results shown in Tables 4 and 5 and Figure 1 were created based on the results of SEM. Table 4 shows the fit measures for the model. It is recommended to have χ^2/df value between 5 and 2, and CFI and TLI values above 0.8 and RMSEA 0.08 or less (see Arbuckle, 2007). Our model satisfies the criteria suggested by Arbuckle (2007).

The results shown in Table 5 suggest that CI positively related to all four HRM practices significantly. Specifically, standardized regression coefficient of 0.618 ($p < 0.001$) reveals that CI significantly positively related to performance management practices, supporting H1. Standardized regression coefficient of 0.462 ($p < 0.001$) reveals that CI significantly positively related to job-related training practices. This supports H2. As predicted in H3, standardized regression coefficient of 0.567 ($p < 0.001$) reveals that CI significantly positively related to employee involvement practices. Finally, standardized regression coefficient of 0.532 ($p < 0.001$) reveals that CI significantly positively related to team work practices, which supports H4.

Table 5 also shows the values of coefficient of determination. The coefficient of determination of 0.382 suggests that CI accounts for 38% of the variation of performance management practices. The coefficient of determination of 0.213 suggests that CI accounts for 21% of the variation of job-related training practices. The coefficient of determination of 0.322 suggests that CI accounts for 32% of the variation of employee involvement practices. Finally, the coefficient of determination of 0.283 suggests that CI accounts for 28% of the variation of team work practices.

Table 4

Table 5

Figure 1

Discussion of findings in relation to implications for the literature and practice

We presented above empirical findings for the effects of CI on performance management, job-related training, employee involvement and team work. The findings have implications for both the existing literature and practice.

Discussion of findings in relation to implications for the literature

With regard to implications for the literature, first, as presented in the section on introduction, the world is witnessing organizations, especially in the developing world, implementing CI initiatives for the survival in local and foreign markets. Such evidence made us to investigate the influence of CI on HRM practices. We presented empirical findings for the effects of CI on HRM practices to provide an understanding of how the HRM practices of performance management, job-related training, employee involvement and team work had been influenced by CI initiatives. The findings supported the hypotheses that CI initiatives have significant effect on all the four HRM practices. In other words, the findings suggest that the implementation of CI demands changes in the way HRM is practiced. To align with CI initiatives, firms have to make changes to the way performance management, job-related training, employee involvement and team work are practiced. This finding supports previous research such as Glover et al. (2011) that stated any CI initiative has inherent HRM implications. Still, a limited number of studies such as Wickramasinghe (2012), Kane (2000) and Monks et al. (1997) investigated changes in the HRM practices due to CI initiatives, and these studies were conducted several years/decades back. Although previous studies such as Mariappanadar and Kramar (2014) Wickramasinghe (2012) and Graso and Probst (2012) suggested that CI initiatives could be used to streamline HRM practices, this has not been empirically tested in the literature on business process improvement. Therefore, this is the most important contribution of the present study. This made the importance of the study to enhance the understanding on this important area.

When specific HRM practices are taken into consideration, the findings suggest that job-related training significantly influenced by CI initiatives. Few previous studies such as Jaca et al. (2016) and Gonzalez and Martins (2016) showed the importance of learning environment to achieve the objectives of CI. However, these studies were not conducted in the context of service delivery. The present study showed that CI affects employees' job-related capabilities in the context of service delivery. The measures used by us captured the importance of training in enhancing service personnel's friendly attitude, expertise in the job task performance and behaviour in providing satisfactory service encounter to customers.

When considering the finding that showed team work significantly influenced by CI initiatives, we have not found any previous study that investigated the effect of CI on team work practices. When taking into consideration that many job tasks are accomplished through teams, the attention paid to this important area is not sufficient. The present study tried to fill this gap in the literature. Further, the findings of the present study seem to contradict with arguments made by Samat et al. (2006) that team work could make employees less responsive to their individual job performance leading to low service delivery. However, it should be noted that we have not come across previous studies on team work in the context of CI, which are similar in nature to our study to make direct comparisons.

When considering the finding that showed employee involvement significantly influenced by CI initiatives, our finding supports Jurburg et al. (2018) in identifying the importance of employee involvement and the need of aligning employee involvement with CI initiatives. Although we showed that CI has significant effect on the way performance of the employees are managed, we have not come across previous studies on the effect of CI on performance management that are similar in nature to the present study to make direct comparisons.

When considering all the HRM practices investigated in the present study, the findings imply the need of changing existing HRM practices in accordance with CI initiatives since CI initiatives have significant effect on the way HRM is practiced. Specifically, the findings suggest that when CI initiatives were implemented to improve the way in which interactions occur between employees and customers during service encounters, those significantly influence the streamlining of the HRM practices. Further, this root of improvements in HRM practices may also lead to develop some sustainable HRM practices enhancing the quality of life of employees at the workplace. Still, the findings imply the need of streamlining HRM practices with a strategic perspective when introducing CI initiatives. Therefore, the findings of our study will be of value, which provide evidence on the effects of CI on the way human resource is

managed. However, we have not come across previous empirical studies with our scope of the study to make direct comparisons.

Overall, our study makes important contributions to the existing literature since we have investigated the effect of CI on several HRM practices in a single study. The measures we used captured the changes occurred in job-related training, performance management, employee involvement and team work when integrating with CI initiatives. Although there are previous studies that investigated each HRM practice separately such as training by Matthews and Marzec (2017), Gonzalez and Martins (2016) and Jaca et al. (2016) or employee involvement by Jurburg et al. (2018), it is very rare to find previous studies that investigated several HRM practices in a single study. Therefore, we believe that the findings of our study provide baseline data that would be a source of general guidance in stimulating future research in this area.

Discussion of findings in relation to implications for practice

With regard to implications for practice, first, all the four HRM practices that we have empirically investigated, i.e., performance management, job-related training, team work and employee involvement, shown to be significantly influenced by CI initiatives. Hence, CI requires continuous changes and adoption by organizational members. Accordingly, HRM practices should also undergo changes to ensure these practices are in alignment with strategic initiatives of organizations. Although previous research suggested the existence of this root of improvements in HRM practices due to CI initiatives (such as Abdullah et al., 2009; Ramayah et al., 2011; Wickramasinghe, 2012), we provided the empirical evidence for the role of CI in developing some sustainable changes in HRM practices enhancing the quality of life of employees at the workplace.

Second, it is possible that CI initiatives operate alongside the command and control structures of conventional management. Therefore, CI initiatives that are aligned with the strategic direction of firms will guide to design and implement better focused HRM practices. Such efforts may lead to increase efficiency as well as build profitable customer relationships. Third, the findings suggest that CI leads to improve how HRM is practiced in service organizations. This implies the need of streamlining HRM practices with a strategic perspective when introducing CI initiatives.

Fourth, the findings imply the need of having a strategic direction across various HRM practices for effective CI implementations. Specially, HR managers should become a part of CI initiatives by designing innovative HRM practices and streamlining the existing HRM practices. However, previous studies such as Sparrow and Otaye-Ebede (2014) and Wickramasinghe and

Mahmood (2018) showed that HR managers rarely take the leading role in the implementation of CI initiatives. Therefore, the findings imply that by acquiring the relevant knowledge and understanding of CI initiatives, HR practitioners would be able to translate CI requirements into HRM practices by streamlining HRM practices in line with CI initiatives aimed at long-term business excellence.

Conclusion

Building on the research gap discussed at the beginning of this article, we investigated how HRM practices could be affected when organizations continuously improve ways in which a particular service is delivered to customers. The study confined to four important HRM practices of performance management, job-related training, team work and employee involvement, and the effect of CI initiatives on these practices. We reviewed the existing literature to support our arguments, and proposed four hypotheses for each HRM practice. The findings of our empirical study supported the hypotheses that CI initiatives significantly positively influence to streamline all the HRM practices investigated. Overall, the findings imply that CI initiatives lead to improve how HRM is practiced in organizations; there is a need of streamlining these practices with a strategic perspective when introducing CI initiatives to develop sustainable HRM practices in organizations. The expectation is to develop a coherent set of HRM practices to support the implementation of CI. Therefore, the present study makes important contributions to the existing literature, which were discussed at length in the previous section under two subheadings of *Implications for the literature* and *Implications for practice*.

Limitations of the study and areas for future research

With regard to the limitations of the study, first, firms we investigated came from a single business sector since we intended to obtain a homogeneous set of firms that had implemented CI initiatives. The data screening had not revealed any significant differences across the firms on our study variables. Therefore, the results can be generalizable. Although homogeneity had given us advantages in interpreting results, future research could expand the focus by including several business sectors. Second, with the systems perspective, HRM practices do not operate in isolation. Therefore, future research could broaden the number of HRM practices under consideration, by examining interrelations between HRM practices, and comparing how CI takes place at different levels in the organization. Third, it is possible that CI initiatives operate alongside the command and control structures of conventional management. Therefore, future research could take into account moderator and mediator relationships involving CI and HRM

practices. It is evident from our study that CI initiatives lead to make changes in the way HRM is practiced. It is also possible to argue that, in the long-run, the streamlining of HRM practices may further strengthen the implementation of CI initiatives, which may further streamline the way HRM is practiced. In the real world, the occurrence of endogeneity is possible for many organizational practices, including CI and HRM. Therefore, future research could test such endogeneity by designing longitudinal research studies.

References

- Abdullah, M.M.B., Uli, J. and Tar, J.J. (2009), "The relationship of performance with soft factors and quality improvement", *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*, Vol. 20 No. 7, pp. 735-748
- Arbuckle, J.L. (2007), *Amos 16.0 User's guide*. Chicago, IL: SPSS Inc.
- Berling, C. (2000), "Continuous improvement as seen from groups and improvement agents", *Total Quality Management*, Vol. 11 Nos. 4/5&6, pp. S48-S489.
- Bessant, J. and Caffyn, S. (1997), "High-involvement innovation through continuous improvement", *International Journal of Technology Management*, Vol. 14 No. 1, <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJTM.1997.001705>
- Bhuiyan, N. and Baghel, A. (2005), "An overview of continuous improvement: From the past to the present", *Management Decision*, Vol. 43 No. 5, pp. 761-771.
- Biron, M., Farndale, E. and Paauwe, J. (2011), "Performance management effectiveness: Lessons from world-leading firms", *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 22 No. 6, pp. 1294-1311.
- Boer, H., Berger, A., Chapman, R. and Gertsen, F. (2000), *CI changes: From suggestion box to organizational learning. Continuous improvement in Europe and Australia*. Ashgate: Aldershot, UK.
- Bourgault, M., Drouin, N. and Hamel, E. (2008), "Decision making within distributed project teams: An exploration of formalization and autonomy as determinants of success", *Project Management Journal*, Vol. 39 (Supplement), S97-S110.
- Brown, A., Eatock, J., Dixon, D., Meenan, B.J. and Anderson, J. (2008), "Quality and continuous improvement in medical device manufacturing", *The TQM Magazine*, Vol. 20 No. 6, pp. 541-555.
- Çiçek, M.C., Köksal, G. and ÖZdemirel, N.E. (2005), "A team performance measurement model for continuous improvement", *Total Quality Management*, Vol. 16, No. 3, pp. 331-349.
- Cooke, F.L. and Kim, S. (2018), *Routledge Handbook of Human Resource Management in Asia*. (Eds). Routledge: Oxon, UK

- Dayan, M. and Di Benedetto, C.A. (2009), "Antecedents and consequences of teamwork quality in new product development projects: An empirical investigation", *European Journal of Innovation Management*, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 129-155.
- de Treville, S. and Antonakis, J. (2006), "Could lean production job design be intrinsically motivating? Contextual, configurational, and levels-of-analysis issues", *Journal of Operations Management*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 99-123.
- De Val, M.P. and Lloyd, B. (2003), "Measuring empowerment", *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 102-108.
- DeNisi, A.S. (2011), "Managing performance to change behavior", *Journal of Organizational Behavior Management*, Vol. 31 No. 4, pp. 262-276.
- Dharmasiri, A.S. (2004), Enhancement of conceptual competencies of Sri Lankan managers for strategic decision making. *Sri Lankan Journal of Management*, Vol. 5 No. 2, pp. 195-227.
- Glover, W.J., Farris, J.A., Van Aken, E.M. and Doolen, T.L. (2011), "Critical success factors for the sustainability of Kaizen event human resource outcomes: An empirical study", *International Journal of Production Economics*, Vol. 132, pp. 197-213.
- Gonzalez, R.V.D. and Martins, M.F. (2016), "Capability for continuous improvement: Analysis of companies from automotive and capital goods industries", *The TQM Journal*, Vol. 28 No.2, pp. 250-274.
- Graso, M. and Probst, T. M. (2012), "The effect of consideration of future consequences on quality and quantity aspects of job performance", *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, Vol. 42 No.6, pp. 1335-1352.
- Gravina, N.E. and Siers, B.P. (2011), "Square pegs and round holes: Ruminations on the relationship between performance appraisal and performance management", *Journal of Organizational Behavior Management*, Vol. 31 No. 4, pp. 277-287.
- Greasley, A. (2004), "Process improvement within a HR division at a UK police force", *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 24 No. 3, pp. 230-240.
- Grönroos, C. (2001), "The perceived service quality concept - a mistake?" *Managing Service Quality*, Vol. 11 No. 3, pp. 150-152.
- Haas, M.R. (2010), "The double-edged swords of autonomy and external knowledge: Analyzing team effectiveness in a multinational organization", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 53 No. 5, 989-1008.
- Hair, J.F. Jr, Black, W.C., Babin, B.J., Anderson, R.E. (2009), *Multivariate data analysis*, 7th ed., New Delhi, India: Pearson.
- Hassan, A., Hashim, J. and Ismail, A.Z.H. (2006), "Human resource development practices as determinant of HRD climate and quality orientation", *Journal of European Industrial Training*, Vol. 30 No. 1, pp. 4-18.

- Hoegl, M. and Gemuenden, H.G. (2001), Teamwork quality and the success of innovative projects: A theoretical concept and empirical evidence, *Organization Science*, Vol. 12 No. 4, pp. 435-449.
- Hur, M.H. (2009), "The influence of total quality management practices on the transformation of how organisations work", *Total Quality Management and Business Excellence*, Vol. 20 No. 8, pp. 847-861.
- Jaca, C., Paipa-Galeano, L., Viles, E. and Mateo, R. (2016), "The impact of a readiness program for implementing and sustaining continuous improvement processes", *The TQM Journal*, Vol. 28 No. 6, pp. 869-886.
- Jimenez-Jimenez, D. and Martinez-Costa, M. (2009), "The performance effect of HRM and TQM: A study in Spanish organizations", *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 29 No. 12, pp. 1266-1289.
- Jurburg, D., Viles, E., Tanco, M. and Mateo, R. (2018), "Continuous improvement leaders, followers and laggards: Understanding system sustainability", *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, Vol. 29 No. 7-8, pp. 817-833.
- Kane, B. (2000), Downsizing, TQM, re-engineering, learning organizations and HRM strategy, *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, Vol. 38 No. 1, pp. 26-49.
- Kanungo, R. (1982), "Measurement of job and work involvement", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 67, pp. 341-349.
- Kaye, M. and Anderson, R. (1999), "Continuous improvement: The ten essential criteria", *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, Vol. 16 No. 5, pp. 485-506.
- Ketkar, S. and Sett, P. K. (2009), "HR flexibility and firm performance: Analysis of a multi-level causal model", *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 20 No. 5, pp. 1009-1038.
- Liao, T.-S., Rice, J. and Martin, N. (2011), "The role of the market in transforming training and knowledge to superior performance: Evidence from the Australian manufacturing sector", *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 22 No. 2, pp. 376-394.
- Lombardi, R., Manfredi, S., Cuzzo, B., and Palmaccio, M. (2020), "The Profitable Relationship Among Corporate Social Responsibility and Human Resource Management: A New Sustainable Key Factor", *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environment Management*, advanced online, <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1990>.
- Mariappanadar, S. and Kramar, R. (2014), "Sustainable HRM: The synthesis effect of high performance work systems on organisational performance and employee harm", *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, Vol. 6 No. 3, pp. 206-224.
- Marin-Garcia, J.A., Val, D.M.P., Martin, T.B. (2008), "Longitudinal study of the results of continuous improvement in an industrial company", *Team Performance Management*, Vol. 14 No. 1/2, pp. 56-69.

- Matthews, R.L. and Marzec, P.E. (2017), "Continuous quality and process improvement: Disintegrating and reintegrating operational improvement?", *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, Vol. 28 No. 3/4, pp. 296-317.
- McCain, S-L.C., Jang, S-C. and Hu, C. (2005), "Service quality gap analysis toward customer loyalty: Practical guidelines for casino hotels", *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, Vol. 24 No. 3, pp. 465-472.
- Milner, C.D. and Savage, B.M. (2016), "Modeling continuous improvement evolution in the service sector: A comparative case study". *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, Vol. 8 No. 3, pp. 438-460.
- Monks, K., Buckley, F. and Sinnott, A. (1997), "Human resource management in a quality context: some Irish evidence", *Employee Relations*, Vol. 19 No. 3, pp. 193-207.
- Ni, W. and Sun, H. (2009), "The relationship among organisational learning, continuous improvement and performance improvement: An evolutionary perspective", *Total Quality Management*, Vol. 20, No. 10, pp. 1041-1054.
- Petrick, J.A. and Furr, D.S. (1995), *Total quality in managing human resources*, St Lucie Press, Delray Beach, FL.
- Prado-Prado, J.C. (2009), "Continuous improvement in the supply chain", *Total Quality Management*, Vol. 20, No. 3, pp. 301-309.
- Ramayah, T., Samat, N. and Lo, M-C. (2011), "Market orientation, service quality and organizational performance in service organizations in Malaysia", *Asia-Pacific Journal of Business Administration*, Vol. 3 No. 1, pp. 8-27.
- Rapp, C. and Eklund, J. (2002), "Sustainable development of improvement activities: The long-term operation of a suggestion scheme in a Swedish company", *Total Quality Management*, Vol. 13 No. 7, pp. 945-969.
- Rijnders, S. and Boer, H. (2004), "A typology of continuous improvement implementation processes", *Knowledge and Process Management*, Vol. 11 No. 4 pp. 283- 296.
- Sajeewanie, T.L., and Opatha, H.H.D.N.P. (2007), Relationships between human resource manager-related factors and practice of strategic human resource management in Sri Lankan listed firms. *Sri Lankan Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 71-87.
- Samat, N., Ramayah, T. and Saad, N.M. (2006), "TQM practices, service quality, and market orientation: Some empirical evidence from a developing country", *Management Research News*, Vol. 29 No. 11, pp. 713-728.
- Shrivastava, A. and Purang, P. (2011), "Employee perceptions of performance appraisals: A comparative study on Indian banks", *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 22 No. 3, pp. 632-647.
- Soltani, E., van der Meer, R., Williams, T.M. and Lai, P. (2006), "The compatibility of performance appraisal systems with TQM principles: evidence from current practice", *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 26 No. 1, pp. 92-112.

- Sparrow, P. and Otaye-Ebede, L. (2014), "Lean management and HR function capability: The role of HR architecture and the location of intellectual capital". *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 25, 2892-2910.
- Spector, P. E. (1994), "Using self-report questionnaires in OB research: A comment on the use of a controversial method" *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 15 No. 5, pp. 385-392.
- Tanco, M., Mateo, R., Santos, J., Jaca, C. and Viles, E. (2012), "On the relationship between continuous improvement programmes and their effect on quality defects: An automotive case study", *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, Vol. 23 No. 3/4, pp. 277-290.
- Terziovski, M. and Sohal, A.S. (2000), "The adoption of continuous improvement and innovation strategies in Australian manufacturing firms", *Technovation*, Vol. 20 No. 10, pp. 539- 550.
- Tjosvold, D. (1984), "Cooperation theory and organizations", *Human Relations*, Vol. 37 No. 9, pp. 743-767.
- Turesky, E.F. and Connell, P. (2010), "Off the rails: Understanding the derailment of a lean manufacturing initiative", *Organization Management Journal*, Vol. 7, pp. 110-132.
- Vouzias, F. (2004), "HR utilization and quality improvement: The reality and the rhetoric – the case of Greek industry", *The TQM Magazine*, Vol. 16 No. 2, pp. 125-135.
- Wickramasinghe, D. and Wickramasinghe, V. (2011), "Differences in organizational factors by lean duration", *Operations Management Research*, Vol. 4 No. 3, pp. 111-126.
- Wickramasinghe, G.L.D. and Wickramasinghe, V. (2016), "Effects of continuous improvement on shop-floor employees' job performance in lean production: The role of lean duration", *Research Journal of Textile and Apparel*, Vol. 20 No. 4, pp. 182-194.
- Wickramasinghe, V. (2012), "Influence of total quality management on human resource management practices: An exploratory study", *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, Vol. 29 No. 8, pp. 836-850.
- Wickramasinghe, V. and Mahmood, M.H. (2018), "Human Resource Management in Bangladesh and Sri Lanka", In F.L. Cooke and S. Kim (Eds.) *Routledge Handbook of Human Resource Management in Asia*, pp. 392-412, Routledge: Oxon, UK
- Wynder, M. (2008), "Employee participation in continuous improvement programs: The interaction effects of accounting information and control, *Australian Journal of Management*, Vol. 33, No. 2, pp. 355-374.

Figure

Figure 1. Research model with standardized estimates (**p < 0.001)

Tables

Table 1. Description on CI methodologies in use

	%*
ISO 9000:2008	91
Balanced Score Card	55
Six Sigma	26
Telecom TL9000	24
Plan-do-check-act (PDCA)	23
eTQM Business Process Framework	6
Malcolm Baldrige	3
Other (includes Quality Risk Management, multiple reaction monitoring, Lean, ISO 27000, People Capability Maturity Model Integration)	7

Note: * Multiple answers, percentages do not add up to 100.

Table 2. Description on types of CI teams in use

	%*
Process improvement teams	67
Quality circles	53
Workplace improvement teams	22
Corrective action teams	19

Note: * Multiple answers, percentages do not add up to 100.

Table 3. Correlations

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1 Implementation of CI initiatives	3.67	.59	.772				
2 Performance management	3.55	.62	.426**	.770			
3 Job-related training	3.59	.66	.326**	.460**	.793		
4 Employee involvement	3.54	.62	.409**	.471**	.429**	.801	
5 Team work	3.47	.73	.423**	.488**	.257**	.480**	.816

* $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$; diagonal entries, square root of average variance extracted; off-diagonal entries, correlations between constructs.

Table 4. Model fit summary

CMIN/DF	GIF	RMSEA	PCLOSE	CFI	PRATIO
4.18	.882	.051	.876	.884	.889

Table 5. Effects of CI on HRM practices

	Estimates	Coefficient of determination
Performance management	.618***	.382
Job-related training	.462***	.213
Employee involvement	.567***	.322
Team work	.532***	.283

Note: *** $p < 0.001$

Appendix 1 – Item measures and summary of results of conformity factor analysis

Variables and item measures	Estimate
CI	
Mechanisms are in place in my organization to raise awareness of CI initiatives	.728
My organization tries to improve core business processes to achieve its strategic goals	.770
My organization tries to eliminate non-value adding activities as far as it can	.775
My organization identifies best practices against which to benchmark CI activities	.786
My organization's commitment to CI is publicised throughout the organization	.785
My organization regularly reviews CI process to evaluate the progress	.798
CI initiatives are integrated with strategic goals of my organization	.761
Cronbach's alpha	.864
AVE	.596
CR	.911
Performance management	
My organization has introduced pre-defined performance targets for each job position	.785
My organization has introduced pre-defined performance targets for each department	.818
My organization has introduced pre-defined performance appraisal standards	.840
My organization has introduced pre-defined individual responsibility of performance	.751
My organization has introduced pre-defined collective responsibilities	.704
My organization now provides continuous feedback of job performance	.714
My organization has introduced a system to monitor performance	.736
Cronbach's alpha	.880
AVE	.593
CR	.897
Job-related training	
Training now provided by my organization are relevant to my job tasks	.747
Employees are now visibly interested in undergoing job-related training	.854
Training aids now utilized by my organization are appreciable	.764
Content of training now provided are relevant to achieve organizational goals	.855
My organization now actively provides job-related training to all employees	.749
Outcomes from training programmes are now evaluated and fed back	.782
Cronbach's alpha	.878
AVE	.629
CR	.910
Employee involvement	
My organization has introduced formal channels for employee involvement	.739
Employees can now contribute directly for the decision-making process	.857
Involvement of front-line staff in the decision-making process is now satisfactory	.860
Involvement of first-level management in the decision-making process is now satisfactory	.831
Involvement of middle-level management in the decision-making process is now satisfactory	.707
Cronbach's alpha	.852
AVE	.642
CR	.899
Team work	
There is frequent communication within the team	.849
The goals for sub-tasks are now accepted by all team members	.837
The team members now contribute for the achievement of team goals in accordance with their specific potential	.758
The team members now support each other as best as they can	.808
Team members now feel proud to be a part of the team	.824
Cronbach's alpha	.872
AVE	.666
CR	.909